

Polarographic Studies of 1-Amidino-2-thiourea (HATU) Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(III)

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Polarographic studies of complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{3+} with ligands *S*-methyl-1-amidino-2-thiourea (HSMATU), *S*-ethyl-1-amidino-2-thiourea (HSEATU), *N*-methyl-1-amidino-2-thiourea (HNMATU) and *N*-ethyl-1-amidino-2-thiourea (HNEATU) have been carried out. *Bis* (ligand) complexes of copper *S*-alkyl-1-amidino-2-thiourea (HSRATU) produced two waves, the first wave being attributed to mono(ligand) complexes. A single step reduction took place in case of Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} complexes while for Co^{3+} complexes, a two-step reduction was observed. Different polarographic parameters calculated for these complexes were compared with those of the biguanide complexes.

POLAROGRAPHIC studies of biguanide (Hbg) and amidinoisourea (Haiu) complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{3+} have been reported¹⁻³. These ligands acting as NN donors stabilise higher oxidation states of metal ions⁴⁻⁵. The ligand 1-amidino-2-thiourea (HATU) behave both as a NN donor and as SN donor¹⁰. Its *S*-alkyl (HSRATU) and *N*-alkyl (HNRATU) derivatives behave only as NN and SN donor, respectively towards metal ions. A large number of metal complexes with these ligands have been reported⁶⁻¹⁰. The ligands HATU and HNRATU, acting as SN donors, stabilise lower oxidation states of metal ions⁹. Polarographic behaviour of these complexes containing NN bonding ligands should be similar to that of biguanide complexes, while those having SN bonding ligands should behave differently. In the present investigation we report the polarographic behaviour of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{3+} complexes of HNRATU and HSRATU.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by the known procedure and purified by repeated recrystallisation from water¹⁰. For polarographic studies, LP 7 polarograph with EZ 7 line recorder was used. Standard calomel electrode served as the reference electrode. The dropping mercury cathode had the capillary characteristic of $2.14 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{1/3}$ at zero applied potential in aqueous solution of 0.5 M KCl and 0.01% gelatin. KCl and gelatin were used as supporting electrolyte and maxima suppressor, respectively for polarographic studies in aqueous solution. The HNRATU complexes, were however, studied in water-methanol (1 : 1) mixture. All the polarographic parameters were calculated according to methods described in the earlier paper¹.

Results and Discussion

The polarograms of bis(SRATU) copper(II) complexes showed two waves whereas that of NRATU revealed only one. The waves were found to be well-defined and diffusion controlled as well as irreversible. The ratio of diffusion currents for the first and second waves remained almost constant, but changed with dilution, temperature and pH. The first wave disappeared almost completely at pH 9.0 and the second at pH 4.6 with decreasing pH, height of the first wave went on increasing. This shows the decomposition of bis-complexes in acidic medium and enhanced stability in alkaline medium are revealed by shift in half-wave potential to more negative values. With increasing dilution and temperature, height of the first wave increased at the expense of the second. The polarogram of mono-complexes showed only one wave. The half-wave potential of this wave was found to be identical to that of the first wave of corresponding bis (ligand) complexes. All these facts prove that the first wave in case of these bis (SRATU)copper(II) complexes is due to the presence of the corresponding 'mono' species formed by dissociation of the present bis-(ligand) complexes, the process being facilitated by dilution and increasing acidity.

The complexes, bis (NRATU) copper(II), however, gave only one reduction wave which started from zero applied potential. The half-wave potential value of this wave (-0.2V vs SCE) showed that this complex is much less stable than that of

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TABLE 1

Complex	$-E_{1/2}$ V		α V ⁻¹		$K_r \times 10^6$ cm sec ⁻¹		Q _a kcal		$D\alpha \times 10^5$ cm sec ⁻¹	10 Dq cm ⁻¹
	(i)	(ii)	(i)	(ii)	(i)	(ii)	(i)	(ii)		
[Cu(HSEATU) ₂]Cl ₂	0.20	0.50 (0.52)	—	0.50 (0.58)	—	9.80 (3.20)	—	7.40 (26.20)	6.70	18690
[Cu(HSMATU) ₂]Cl ₂	0.17	0.53 (0.55)	—	0.43 (0.46)	—	7.40 (3.40)	—	5.00 (26.90)	6.70	18560
[Cu(HNEATU) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	0.21	—	—	0.60	—	8.90	—	3.80	—	17230
[Cu(HNMATU) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	0.20	—	—	0.60	—	8.90	—	3.80	—	17160
[Ni(HSEATU) ₂]Cl ₂	—	1.25 (1.50)	—	0.48 (0.58)	—	—	—	—	—	22961
[Ni(HSMATU) ₂]Cl ₂	—	1.30 (1.54)	—	0.50 (0.59)	—	—	—	—	—	22870
[Ni(HNEATU) ₂]Cl ₂	—	1.15	—	0.45	—	—	—	—	—	21101
[Ni(HNMATU) ₂]Cl ₂	—	1.39	—	0.46	—	—	—	—	—	20818
[Co(HSEATU) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	0.68 (0.33)	1.15 (1.21)	0.28 (0.87)	0.30 (0.67)	14.00 (13.00)	76.00 (32.00)	6.00 (9.80)	7.60 (14.40)	9.50	24462
[Co(HSMATU) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	0.70 (0.85)	1.20 (1.24)	0.38 (0.82)	0.50 (0.62)	25.00 (38.00)	81.00 (91.00)	7.80 (9.60)	10.00 (12.80)	9.50	24350

its *S*-alkyl counterpart. Plot of *pH* vs $E_{1/2}$ gave nearly straight lines for the first one showing decomposition at *pH* 5.0 for Cu(SEATU)₂²⁺ and *pH* 5.5 for Cu(SMATU)₂²⁺, respectively. Cu(NRATU)₂²⁺, however, started decomposing at *pH* 6.0 and the waves obtained at -0.2 V during polarographic reduction was mostly due to the decomposed or dissociated product, the dissociation being easier as these are much less stable than the other type of complexes.

The half-wave potential values of these complexes were found to be less negative than the corresponding alkyl-substituted biguanide complexes (Table 1). This fact and the values of other parameters prove that these complexes are less stable than the similar biguanide complexes.

All the nickel(II) complexes produced ill-defined and drawn-out waves. The *pH* vs $E_{1/2}$ plots in case of all these complexes gave two intersecting straight lines, showing their decomposition. The *N*-substituted complexes were found to start decomposing at *pH* as high as 6.0. This also proved the lower stability of these complexes as compared to their *S*-substituted counterparts as found in the case of copper complexes. The first wave is however, absent in the case of bis-complexes of nickel(II) which is also the case for bis-(biguanide) nickel(II) complexes². Absence of the first wave may be due to the non-existence of mono-complexes.

All the cobalt(III) complexes gave two-step well-defined polarographic waves as was also the case for cobalt(III) biguanide³. The first wave correspond to one-electron and the second one to a two-electron transfer process. Varying *pH* had little effect on the reduction process excepting small changes in $E_{1/2}$ values. The ratio of first diffusion current value to the second (i'_d/i''_d) remained almost constant with increasing temperature or dilution (Table 1). The waves shifted to more positive direction (*i.e.* $E_{1/2}$) values were found to be more and more positive with increasing temperature. This fact again proved irreversibility of the electron transfer

processes,

Irreversibility was verified by $\log i_E/(i_a - i_E)$ vs E plots (Table 1). Although expected from the nature of the ligands, no polarographic wave corresponding to M^I ($M = \text{Cu, Ni and Co}$) valency state was observed. The ligand HNRATU, however, produced Cu^I complex in solid state⁹. The reason for not obtaining polarographic wave in case of NRATU complexes of copper(I) is most probably due to its complete insolubility in any solvent, while in other cases, it is attributed to non-existence in that state.

From the above discussion, it can be inferred that NRATU complexes are less stable than the corresponding SRATU complexes, which in turn are less stable than the similar biguanide complexes. This was revealed by their lower values of activation energy as obtained from $\log K$ vs $1/T$ plots and less negative values of half-wave potential and forward rate constant of the electrode process. The trend is, however, expected from the relative stability of the ligand themselves: $\text{bg} > \text{SRATU} > \text{NRATU}$, as obtained from the spectral data (10 Dq values) (Table 1)

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